

Neuromarketing Practices and Customers' Impulsive Buying Behaviour of Products Sold in Shopping Malls in South-South Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of neuromarketing practices on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria. The study used the cross-sectional survey research design. The population of the study consists of customers from selected shopping malls located in major cities in South-South Nigeria. The study focused on the sample size of 384 customers. The study used stratified sampling technique. The research employed a structured questionnaire as the primary data collection instrument. In order to ascertain the instrument's reliability, a test-retest approach was used. Data collected were analyzed using multiple regression and correlation analysis. Findings showed that audio sensitivity, emotional branding, scent marketing, store atmosphere, and visual appeal had significant positive effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour. The study concluded that neuromarketing practices had significant positive effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria. The study recommended amongst others that shopping malls should be encouraged to use a visually captivating design that incorporates uniform signage, branding features, and aesthetics over the entirety of the mall.

Keywords: Customers' Impulsive Buying Behaviour, Neuromarketing Practices, Visual Appeal

1.1 Introduction

In the age of globalisation, the evolution of a progressively dynamic and competitive business environment necessitates that organisations alter their approach to product offerings, product maintenance, consumer attraction, and competitor management. Recently, there have been notable advances in the field of consumer behaviour, particularly in the decision-making process and its impact on purchase intention (Stankevich, 2017). The markets are distinctive

and distinguished by increased competition, ongoing innovation in already-existing goods and services, and a greater presence of businesses within the same market. Having a thorough understanding of the consumer is crucial in this situation (Varadarajan, 2020). By analysing the aspects that directly influence consumer behaviour, it becomes feasible to innovate and fulfil their expectations. Marketers must possess this skill in order to enhance their campaigns and effectively engage the intended audience (Ding, DeSarbo, Hanssens, Jedidi, Lynch, & Lehmann, 2020).

Neuromarketing is a significant marketing approach that focuses on measuring three essential factors in consumer behaviour: attention, emotional commitment, and retention (Mustafa, 2022). Neuromarketing employs intangible notions that may initially appear immeasurable to drive marketing efforts. The main objective of neuromarketing is to enhance comprehension and forecast consumer behaviour (Cherubino, Martinez-Levy, Caratù, Cartocci, Di Flumeri, Modica, Rossi, Mancini, & Trettel, 2019). The ability to gain insight into the thought processes of customers has given firms a valuable opportunity to enhance their understanding of consumer behaviour, which is the foundation of an individual's decision-making process (Kari, Arun, & Pundir, 2020). Neuromarketing is a neuroscience technique that involves comprehending the cognitive processes of consumers (de Souza & Pohl, 2018). Neuromarketing has become increasingly popular as a way of influencing customers to purchase a product. Neuromarketing is an innovative approach to discerning customer traits and gathering insights about their motivations, emotional reactions, attitudes, and cognitive functions. Neuromarketing is a valuable method for quantifying the impact of commercials without requiring client involvement and elucidating their emotional responses when exposed to an advertisement (Liu, Zhao, Xiong, & Ren, 2023). Neuromarketing has greatly enhanced the quality of advertisements and is valuable for enhancing the efficacy of advertising efforts.

Visual branding components, including colours, typography, and imagery, have the ability to communicate a brand's personality and values (Choon-Lee, 2019). For instance, dynamic and lighthearted graphics could attract a young and lively demographic, while sleek and understated aesthetics may resonate with individuals in search of simplicity and elegance. When the visual branding is in harmony with consumers' interests and values, it has the potential to establish a connection and have an influence on their purchasing choices (Di, Wang, Nie, & Li, 2022). Nevertheless, maintaining a regular audio branding strategy contributes to the establishment of brand familiarity. Repeated exposure to a brand's sound elements, such as a jingle or audio emblem, leads to the incorporation of these elements into customers' memories. This awareness can lead to a sense of familiarity and trust, increasing the likelihood that consumers will choose the well-known brand over competitors when making purchasing decisions.

Scent marketing has the potential to shape customers' perceptions of a brand and its products. Companies can establish a distinctive sensory encounter that corresponds to their intended brand image by linking a particular fragrance to their brand (Cao & Duong, 2021). For instance, a bakery that utilises the aroma of recently baked pastries can elicit a feeling of cosiness, genuineness, and excellence. Such influence can have a beneficial impact on

customers' impressions of the brand and its products, resulting in heightened trust and a greater inclination to make a purchase. Emotional branding has the ability to transform people into enthusiastic advocates for a brand. Customers that have a deep emotional attachment to a brand are more inclined to participate in word-of-mouth marketing, share their positive experiences on social media, and actively endorse the company to others (Meylano, Respati, & Firdiansjah, 2020). This advocacy has the potential to enhance brand recognition, expand the client base, and strengthen emotional connections.

Neuromarketing methods offer valuable information for assessing the efficacy of advertising efforts in influencing consumers in the realm of online shopping (Singh, 2020). Neuromarketing has been employed to investigate the process of making purchasing decisions and consumer behaviour. Its aim is to enhance the understanding of products and sales marketing strategies, making them more impactful by identifying the specific areas and methods that elicit the strongest response from consumers (Jordão, De Souza, de Oliveira, & Giraldi, 2017). Neuromarketing is a multidisciplinary domain that seeks to better understand customer behaviour by examining the brain using many approaches, including neuroimaging. The research seeks to quantify the influence of market stimuli on individuals, thereby offering novel insights into how consumers store, integrate, interpret, and use the vast array of information they get on a daily basis. Neuromarketing involves the use of neuroscience principles in the field of marketing. Neuromarketing is the practice of directly utilising brain pictures, scans, or other technologies that monitor brain activity to assess how individuals respond to particular items, packaging, advertising, or other parts of marketing (Devaru, 2018). The study seeks to analyse the effect of neuromarketing strategies on customers' impulsive buying behaviour.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In the pursuit of optimising marketing strategies and strengthening their competitive edge, businesses acknowledge the significance of acquiring a profound understanding of the underlying subconscious elements that influence customer decision-making. Conventional marketing methods sometimes fail to fully grasp the fundamental reasons and emotional stimuli that impact customers' buying decisions. Neuromarketing, an interdisciplinary field integrating neuroscience, psychology, and marketing, presents a highly promising approach. Through the use of strategies such as neuroimaging, gaze tracking, and biometric assessments, enterprises can acquire a more comprehensive comprehension of how consumers see, process, and react to marketing stimuli. Neuromarketing is a field that is not widely exploited due to the conservative mindset of retailers, who believe that modern strategies are time-consuming and demand significant effort. Despite its recent surge in popularity, consumer preference, or the reasons behind why individuals choose one product over another, is a significant focus for organisations in today's market. Nevertheless, the development of a successful neuromarketing plan necessitates the resolution of certain crucial obstacles.

It is necessary to determine the precise psychological mechanisms that impact customers' impulsive purchasing behaviour. Comprehending the influence of sensory clues, emotional responses, and cognitive biases on decision-making can assist marketers in creating more compelling and focused campaigns. Executing neuromarketing strategies requires substantial financial and technological resources. The process of obtaining and examining neuroscientific data can be costly, and the knowledge needed to interpret the findings is usually specialized. Most firms want pragmatic ideas and precise guidance to efficiently deploy neuromarketing initiatives.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to examine the effect of neuromarketing practices on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. assess the effect of audio sensitivity on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria.
- ii. explore the effect of emotional branding on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria.
- iii. ascertain the effect of scent marketing on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria.
- iv. assess the effect of store atmosphere on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria.
- v. determine the effect of visual appeal on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria.

1.4 Research Hypotheses

H0₁: Audio sensitivity has no significant effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria.

H0₂: Emotional branding has no significant effect customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria.

H0₃: Scent marketing has no significant effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria.

H0₄: Store atmosphere has no significant effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria.

H0₅: Visual appeal has no significant effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Neuromarketing Practices

Neuromarketing can be defined as the intersection of neuroscience, psychology, and marketing, with a specific emphasis on studying the emotional and cognitive responses of consumers to marketing stimuli (Li, 2019). The objective is to effectively communicate commercial messages to others and enhance the likelihood of customer purchase, thereby reducing marketing and advertising expenses (Mansor & Isa, 2020). Neuromarketing is applied in two main areas. The first area involves studying consumer behaviour and decision-making using neuroscience (Babiloni & Cherubino, 2020; Clark, 2020). The second area focuses on using neurocommunication to stimulate mental processes and encourage desirable consumer behaviours (Fenger, 2015). Quinteros and Martínez (2018) argued that neuromarketing serves as a stimulus for consumer purchasing decisions through advertising in the retail industry. Neuromarketing is an interdisciplinary field that integrates the principles of neuroscience with marketing in order to comprehend and manipulate customer behaviour. When formulating a neuromarketing plan, multiple aspects are involved. Several neuroimaging methods, including functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), electroencephalography (EEG), and eye-tracking, can offer valuable insights into how consumers react to marketing stimuli. These techniques facilitate the identification of brain activity patterns linked to attention, emotion, memory, and decision-making.

Neuromarketing is the practice of using physiological and brain signals to understand customers' motives, preferences, and decisions. This information can be used to enhance creative advertising, product development, pricing, and other marketing strategies (Harrell, 2019). Neuromarketing is a revolutionary approach in the marketing field that draws from neuroscience-oriented disciplines such as psychology, neurology, marketing, and economics. It focuses on understanding the consumer and the various factors that influence their individual preferences and consumption behaviour. By using neuroscientific techniques applied to marketing management, it analyses emotions, attention, and memory at different levels, with a particular emphasis on the subconscious. The unique aspect of neuromarketing lies in its use of neuroscience techniques to gain a deeper understanding of customers, their true preferences, and what motivates commercial transactions (Duque, 2014). Emotional reactions to marketing stimuli play a crucial role in neuromarketing (Bastiaansen et al., 2018). People make purchasing decisions based on the emotions they experience, and these emotions create lasting impressions in memory regarding how a brand or company is regarded (González-Morales, 2020).

The phrases consumer neuroscience and neuromarketing have been consistently used in marketing literature, often interchangeably or synonymously. Irrespective of their lexical and semantic usage, these are pragmatically distinct for certain authors. Consumer neuroscience refers to academic research that integrates neuroscience, psychology, and biology to elucidate specific human behaviours in context, such as consumption or voting behaviours.

Neuromarketing, on the other hand, is viewed more practically and commercially as a collection of neurophysiological techniques employed by market research companies or practitioners (Javor, Koller, Lee, Chamberlain, & Ransmayr, 2013). Nemorin (2018) defines neuromarketing as a commercialised approach to market research that utilises the techniques of cognitive neuroscience and behavioural psychology to study brain activity. Its purpose is to gain deeper insights into consumer responses to products, brands, and advertising stimuli.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher's conceptualization (2024)

2.1.2 Visual Appeal

Visual appeal refers to the display of typefaces and other visual components, such as images, that improve the overall appearance of a system (Parboteeah, Valacich, & Wells, 2009). During the stages before purchasing and using a product, its visual attractiveness plays a crucial role in inspiring purchasers to explore it and helps efficient information retrieval (Zheng, Men, Yang, & Gong, 2019). This, in turn, increases the likelihood of taking action (Lee & Kacen, 2008). Thus, Zheng et al.'s (2019) study considers visual appeal as a stimulus that impacts consumers' affective and cognitive responses. In addition, the aesthetic attractiveness of information and design elicits favourable feelings and hence stimulates impulsive buying behaviour (Liu et al., 2013), particularly among younger consumers (Djafarova & Bowes, 2021).

Xiang, Zheng, Lee, and Zhao (2016) verified that the visual appeal of an online store's graphic display has the ability to augment consumers' virtual haptic experience, hence promoting the

occurrence of intense positive emotions, also known as perceived delight. Moreover, a recent study has shown that the visual attractiveness of mobile commerce has a beneficial impact on consumers' perceptions of enjoyment (Zhang, Leng, & Liu, 2020). Eye gaze, or eye tracking, is a technology extensively used in the field of neuromarketing. Eye tracking technology quantifies either the gaze direction of the audience or the eye movements in relation to a person's head. It primarily quantifies the duration of a person's gaze on a specific area or the orientation of a person's gaze towards an object (Sharma, Dash, & Deshmukh, 2023). Visual branding entails effectively crafting a memorable encounter for consumers that instills trust in the organisation, thereby generating brand recommendations, fostering client loyalty, and encouraging good word-of-mouth if the experience was exceptional (Sardovski, 2022). Visually well-crafted elements, such as a sophisticated logo, attractive packaging, and top-notch photography, have the ability to generate a favourable perception and indicate that the brand provides superior products or services (Khare & Singh, 2020). This can impact consumers' perception of the brand as dependable and credible, thereby enhancing their inclination to make a purchase.

2.1.3 Audio Sensitivity

Audio branding, alternatively referred to as sonic branding or sound branding, involves the strategic utilisation of sound and music components to establish a unique and recognisable character for a brand. Similar to visual branding, which uses logos, colours, and typography to symbolise a brand, audio branding centres around the deliberate use of sound to strengthen brand identification, elicit emotions, and establish a memorable and uniform brand encounter. According to Minsky and Fahey (2017), a sound brand is a concise and unique melody or series of sounds, typically placed at the start or finish of a commercial. It is generally accompanied by a visual logo to enhance brand awareness. Developing a distinct and easily identifiable sound identity for a brand using original music compositions or catchy tunes. This can entail the development of a brand theme or the integration of particular musical motifs that symbolise the values and characteristics of the brand (Hudson, Roth, Madden, & Hudson, 2015). Creating succinct audio logos or mnemonic devices that function as short auditory embodiments of a brand. These brief audio excerpts frequently accompany graphic logos in ads, introductions, and conclusions. The process of establishing a consistent voice or sound for a brand involves carefully selecting voice-over artists, narrators, or vocal elements that accurately represent the company's tone, personality, and values (Baraybar-Fernández, Baños-González, Barquero-Pérez, Goya-Esteban, & de-la-Morena-Gómez, 2017). The inclusion of amusing elements in the design, music, and substance of an advertisement is seen as a contributing component to its humour (Bellman et al., 2017). Deconstructive characteristics of humour, such as irrelevance, mimicry, impersonation, anomalies, irrational repetitions, and humorous appearances, have an impact on capturing attention and enhancing memory retention. Through the strategic use of appropriate sounds, melodies, and tones, audio branding can effectively elicit a favourable emotional reaction in customers. This can result in heightened brand loyalty and a higher probability of making a purchase (Cherubino et al., 2019). Audio branding has the potential to greatly influence customer purchasing behaviour through several channels.

2.1.4 Scent Marketing

Scent marketing, also known as olfactory marketing or aroma marketing, involves the deliberate use of particular odours or perfumes to establish a favourable and lasting brand encounter and manipulate consumer behaviour. It uses the olfactory sense to actively involve customers, amplify their emotions, and establish a unique connection with a brand or product. The connection between smell and memory is established due to the neuroanatomy of the brain (Walsh, 2020). Exploiting the capacity of the sense of smell to trigger specific memories and generate vivid experiences is a novel marketing tactic that can enhance the connection and loyalty of customers to a particular brand (Gottschalk, 2018). Scent marketing is a specialised area that focuses on using fragrances strategically to establish lucrative connections with clients, which is often overlooked since it is not easily quantifiable. Therefore, its efficacy in enticing and eliciting impulsive buying choices from clients in a point-of-sale situation has been demonstrated (Liburyt & Vaitiek, 2019). Like visual branding, fragrance branding seeks to establish a distinctive and recognisable sensory character for a brand. Through the establishment of a connection between a particular fragrance and a brand, firms can stimulate the awareness of scents and cultivate a powerful memory link within the brains of consumers (Biswas & Szocs, 2019). This can result in enhanced brand recognition and help distinguish the brand from its competitors. When buyers link a specific scent with a particular product or product category, it might improve their perception of the product's qualities, such as its freshness, cleanliness, or elegance (Gottschalk, 2018). This can have a favourable influence on buying decisions since customers are more inclined to select things that they perceive as being of superior quality.

2.1.5 Emotional Branding

Emotional branding is a marketing tactic that prioritises the establishment of a powerful emotional bond between a brand and its intended consumer base. It entails utilising emotions, like joy, nostalgia, enthusiasm, or trust, to establish a profound and enduring bond with clients. Emotional branding acknowledges that consumers' purchasing decisions are influenced by their emotions rather than purely rational factors (Srimulyo & Mardiyah, 2020). Brands can establish a more profound and significant bond by eliciting favourable emotions. This emotional bond nurtures brand loyalty, endorsements, and enduring relationships with customers. Emotional branding enables brands to articulate their personality, beliefs, and identity. Through the strategic alignment of a brand's messaging and visual aspects with particular emotions, brands may mould their image and establish a distinct identity that sets them apart from competitors (Meylano, Respati, & Firdiansjah, 2020). Establishing a well-defined brand personality and values that strongly resonate with people can result in more robust emotional connections. Emotional branding encompasses more than just conventional marketing messages and encompasses the entirety of the customer experience (Srimulyo & Mardiyah, 2020). Brands prioritise the creation of favourable and unforgettable experiences at every point of contact, starting from the first interaction and extending to the support provided after a purchase. Brands may improve consumer happiness, loyalty, and advocacy by taking into account the emotional impact of each contact. Emotionally compelling marketing campaigns, narratives, or

brand encounters have the potential to stimulate customers' inclination to make a purchase, hence increasing conversion rates and sales (Ellina et al., 2020). Emotional branding has the ability to elicit favourable word-of-mouth and social influence.

2.1.6 Store atmosphere

The store atmosphere refers to the deliberate design of a retail environment with the aim of eliciting specific emotional responses from shoppers, hence enhancing the likelihood of making purchases (Akram et al., 2016). Utami (2017) defines store atmosphere as the physical attributes of a business, including its architecture, layout, signboards, displays, lighting, air temperature, and aroma. These attributes collectively contribute to creating a pleasant ambiance and shaping the company's image in the eyes of consumers. The store atmosphere refers to the aesthetic elements that create a pleasant and captivating ambiance, aiming to delight clients during their visit to the store (Steven, Pasla, & Hellyani, 2023). Establishing a favourable impression on the consumer is crucial, as it directly influences the customer's perception of the firm. Atmosphere refers to the deliberate arrangement of visual communication, lighting, colours, music, and fragrances in order to shape customers' emotional responses and impressions, ultimately influencing their purchasing behaviour (Kotler & Keller, 2012). Hence, it is evident that the store atmosphere is a crucial, tangible attribute that holds significant importance for every organisation.

This factor is crucial in establishing a pleasant environment for customers, encouraging them to spend more time in the store, and ultimately motivating them to make purchases (Fuad & Hadiati, 2014). The store atmosphere is one of the aspects that affect purchasing decisions. This is supported by the research conducted by Hanafitrah and Widiartanto (2018), which demonstrates that the ambiance of a store has a favourable and substantial impact on consumers' purchase choices. Consequently, a store's ability to cultivate a favourable atmosphere directly correlates with an increased consumer propensity to make purchases of the store's provided products. According to the findings of a prior study conducted by Hidayat and Sujud (2019), it is evident that the ambiance of a business has a substantial impact on consumers' purchasing choices. Consequently, the ambiance within the store can influence a consumer's purchasing choice.

The store atmosphere is a crucial physical attribute for every retail firm. It involves creating a comfortable environment that aligns with consumer preferences, encouraging them to spend more time in the store, and ultimately motivating them to make purchases (Basyir, 2019). Consequently, consumers' purchasing inclination will consistently escalate due to a pleasant store ambiance that consistently strives to create a homely environment and encourage customers to spend more time in the store (Hendrayani, 2019). Paila (2018) demonstrates that the retail atmosphere exerts a substantial impact on purchasing intent. Puspitasari and Yuniati (2016) asserted that the atmosphere exerts a substantial impact on shopping decisions by affecting buying interest. The store atmosphere is one of the aspects that can stimulate impulsive buying. A well-designed store atmosphere can create a sense of comfort and familiarity for consumers, encouraging them to spend longer time in the store and thus increasing their likelihood of making purchases (Hussain & Siddiqui, 2019). The ambiance and

perception of the environment, both external and internal, in a store can create a memorable shopping experience that is hard for consumers to forget.

2.1.7 Customers Impulsive Buying Behaviour

Impulse purchases occur when individuals experience a rapid and intense emotional desire, resulting in reactive behaviour with little cognitive control (Burton, Gollins, McNeely, & Walls, 2018). Impulsive shopping, which involves emotional elements, can be instigated by various factors such as the ambiance of the store, personal fulfilment, self-worth, and the emotional condition of the consumer at the moment (Gogoi & Shillong, 2020). Rodrigues, Lopes, and Varela (2021) posited that impulse purchases can be triggered by an unforeseen necessity, a visual stimulus, a promotional effort, and/or a reduction in cognitive capacity to assess the pros and cons of the purchase. Impulse buying arises from an emotional inability to regulate oneself, resulting from the conflict between immediate gratification and the potential bad outcomes of a purchase. This conflict can lead to compulsive behaviours that may persist and develop pathologically over time (Pandya & Pandya, 2020). Sohn and Ko (2021) contend that while all impulse purchases can be categorised as unplanned, not all unplanned purchases can be classified as impulsive. Unplanned purchases may arise when a consumer has a need to buy a product that was not previously included in their shopping list. This implies that spontaneous purchases do not always involve the immediate craving that typically defines impulsive buying. Impulse purchases are influenced by sensory stimuli such as the store ambiance and product arrangement. Therefore, purchases conducted in physical stores are generally more impulsive compared to internet purchases. Online shopping may be less conducive to impulsive purchases compared to shopping in physical stores due to the absence of sensory stimulation that the internet lacks (Moreira, Fortes, & Santiago, 2017).

2.2 Theoretical Review

Theory of Cognitive Processing and Decision Making

The study was anchored on the theory of cognitive processing and decision-making. Herbert Simon's research during the 1950s on decision-making, bounded rationality, and administrative behaviour provided the first foundations for comprehending the impact of cognitive processes on decision-making. This theory centres on the cognitive processes associated with consumer decision-making. It indicates that customers employ systematic cognitive processing while assessing and selecting products or brands. According to the Theory of Cognitive Processing and Decision Making, consumers employ methodical cognitive processes while assessing and selecting products or brands. This theory highlights the significance of cognitive elements, like attention, information processing, and decision-making biases, in influencing customer behaviour. Neuromarketing tools, such as eye-tracking or implicit association tests (IAT), offer valuable insights into the cognitive processes, attention allocation, and hidden biases that impact consumer decisions.

3. Methodology

Research Design

The study employed the cross-sectional survey research design approach. The cross-sectional survey research design captured a brief and instantaneous representation of the population being studied. The reason for choosing this method is its capacity to assist the researcher in assessing the perspective of the participant and collecting data by administering a survey instrument at a certain moment in time.

Population and sample size

The population of the study consists of customers from selected shopping malls located in major cities in south-south Nigeria. The study focused on customers in 4 States Capital in South-South Nigeria due to easy accessibility and convenience for data collection by the researcher. The researcher collected data from customers of Asaba City Mall (Shoprite) Delta State, Shoprite Nigeria, Warri Delta State, City Mall Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Shopping Mall (MM2) Supermarket, Benin City, Edo State, and Port Harcourt Mall Rivers State. The population was collected within an observed period from when they were officially open to customers to 2 hours before closure during the week. The south-south region of Nigeria is made up of six states. They are: Akwa Ibom State, Bayelsa State, Cross River State, Delta State, Edo State, and Rivers State.

Since it is not possible to study all the customers' of shopping malls in Nigeria, the researcher selected a sample of existing customers of shopping malls in south-south Nigeria. This approach helped to ensure that the sample was representative of the larger population of customers. The Cochran (1977) formula, as cited by Ezenta and Osagie (2021), is a method usually employed to determine sample size in research with an unknown population size. The process entails formulating assumptions regarding the necessary degree of accuracy, the intended level of certainty, and an anticipated proportion of the population exhibiting a specific attribute or behaviour.

The formula for the Cochran sample size calculation is as follows:

$$n = z^2 pq / e^2$$

Where:

n = sample size

z = z-score corresponding to the desired level of confidence

p = estimated proportion of the population with the characteristic or behavior of interest

q = 1 - p

e = level of precision desired (margin of error)

$$n = \frac{Z^2PQ}{e^2}$$

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{0.05^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{0.025}$$

n = 384

Sampling Technique

The study employed the stratified sampling technique. The implementation of stratified sampling technique facilitated the systematic categorization of participants, hence improving their accessibility. The aforementioned approach entailed dividing a diverse population into several uniform subgroups, each of which is internally uniform, and thereafter selecting units at random from each of these subgroups.

Method of Data Collection

The study used a well-structured questionnaire as the main tool for collecting data. A pilot study was conducted to subject the research instrument to some forms of scrutiny before full-scale use. The pilot study involved the distribution of 12 copies of the questionnaire to sample respondents in one of the selected shopping mall to pretest the questionnaire and enable the performance of reliability tests. A preliminary assessment of the questionnaire was conducted on a subset of individuals who possessed comparable background traits to those enrolled in the study. To determine the instrument's reliability, a test-retest approach was employed. Reliability of each concept was determined by assessing internal consistency using the Cronbach alpha index. Hair et al. (2006) asserted that the minimum acceptable range in quantitative research is between 0.60 and 0.70. The Cronbach alpha values computed from table 1 range from 0.717 to 0.734, which above the required threshold of 0.7 for acceptable Cronbach alpha. This indicates that the model's reliability is deemed acceptable.

Table 1. Reliability coefficients of study constructs

Dimension of study constructs	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Audio Sensitivity	5	0.717
Emotional Branding	5	0.719
Scent Marketing	5	0.724
Store Atmosphere	5	0.734
Visual Appeal	5	0.721
Customers Impulsive Buying Behaviour	5	0.729

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Methods of Data Analysis

In order to accomplish the specified research objectives, the study employed quantitative data analysis. The study employed a combination of descriptive and inferential statistical techniques to analyse the data. Significant data were derived by statistical techniques, including frequency distributions for descriptive analysis and correlation, as well as multiple regressions for inferential analysis. Multiple regression analysis is a valuable technique for determining the statistical relationship between two or more variables and for predicting the value of one variable based on the others. The data analyses were conducted using version 25 of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS), a statistical software. The equation's general form for prediction is as follows:

$$CIBB = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AS + \beta_2 EB + \beta_3 SMK + \beta_4 SA + \beta_5 VA + \varepsilon$$

Where:

CIBB= Customers Impulsive Buying Behaviour

AST= Audio Sensitivity

EB= Emotional Branding

SM= Scent Marketing

SA= Store Atmosphere

VA= Visual Appeal

4. Results and Discussion

Table 2. Response Rate

S/N	Questionnaire	Number	Percentage
1	Copies of questionnaire administered	384	100
2	Copies of questionnaire retrieved	375	98
3	Unreturned copies of questionnaire	9	2

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 showed that out of the 384 copies of questionnaire administered, 375(98%) copies were retrieved and were properly filled. Therefore, the analysis in this chapter was based on the response rate of 98%.

Table 3. Frequency Analysis of Respondents Profile

S/N	Characteristics of the Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Gender:		
	Male	206	55
	Female	169	45
	Total	375	100
2	Age Range:		
	Below 30	94	25
	31-40	113	30
	Above 41	168	45
	Total	375	100
3	Marital Status:		
	Single	146	39
	Married	188	50
	Divorced	41	11
	Total	375	100
4	Educational qualification:		
	OND/ NCE	79	21
	HND/ BSc	229	61
	MSc/MBA	67	18
	Total	375	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 indicated on the gender composition that 206 of the respondents representing 55% of the sample were male, while 169 being 45% were female. The age bracket of the respondents showed that 94 of the respondents being 25% were below 30 years of age; 113 of the respondents representing 30% falls within the age bracket of 31-40 years of age; lastly, 168 of the respondents representing 45% were above 41 years of age. The marital composition of the respondents indicated that; 146 of the sample respondents were single being 39%, 188 of the respondents being 50% were married, while 41 other respondents being 11% were divorced. On the educational background of the sample, it was indicated that most of the respondents have a high level of those with tertiary background with 229 respondents representing 61% being HND/ BSc holders; while 79 respondents being 21% of the sample size were OND/ NCE holders, while 67 respondents being 18% of the sample size were MSc/MBA holders.

Table 4. Neuromarketing Practices and Customers' Impulsive Buying Behaviour Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	-14.690	1.238		-11.870	.000		
Audio sensitivity	.417	.040	.318	10.330	.000	.508	1.970
Emotional branding	.415	.030	.393	13.791	.000	.592	1.689
Scent marketing	.110	.042	.068	2.623	.009	.708	1.412
Store atmosphere	.215	.032	.165	6.816	.000	.824	1.214
Visual appeal	.439	.037	.310	12.000	.000	.723	1.382

a. Dependent Variable: Customers' impulsive buying behaviour

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4 showed that audio sensitivity ($\beta = 0.318$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$), emotional branding ($\beta = 0.393$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$), scent marketing ($\beta = 0.068$, $p = 0.009 < 0.05$), store atmosphere ($\beta = 0.165$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) and visual appeal ($\beta = 0.310$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) had significant positive effect on customers impulsive buying behaviour.

The regression model was, therefore;

$$\text{CIBB} = -14.690 + 0.417\text{AS} + 0.415\text{EB} + 0.110\text{SMK} + 0.215\text{SA} + 0.439\text{VA}$$

Table 5 Fitness of the Models

Model		ANOVA ^a				
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	414.313	5	82.863	341.776	.000 ^b
	Residual	89.463	369	.242		
	Total	503.776	374			

a. Dependent Variable: Customers' impulsive buying behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Visual appeal, Store atmosphere, Scent marketing, Emotional branding, Audio sensitivity

The results in table 5 showed that the independent variables were good indicators of neuromarketing practices. This was supported by the F measurement of 341.776 and the p value (0.000) which was less than 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the models were statistically significant.

Table 6 Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.907 ^a	.822	.820	.492

a. Predictors: (Constant), Visual appeal , Store atmosphere , Scent marketing , Emotional branding , Audio sensitivity

Table 6 indicated that the variables of neuromarketing practices explained 82% of the variations in customers' impulsive buying behaviour.

Table 7 Correlations Coefficients for Study Variables

S/N	Study Variables	N	1	2	3	4	5	
1	Audio sensitivity	375	1					
2	Emotional branding	375	0.547 ^{**}	1				
3	Scent marketing	375	0.440 ^{**}	0.491 ^{**}	1			
4	Store atmosphere	375	0.366 ^{**}	0.151 ^{**}	0.092	1		
5	Visual appeal	375	0.454 ^{**}	0.407 ^{**}	0.204 ^{**}	-0.004	1	
6	Customers' impulsive buying behaviour	375	0.764 ^{**}	0.752 ^{**}	0.480 ^{**}	0.345 ^{**}	0.627 ^{**}	1

^{**}. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

^{*}. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 7 indicated that audio sensitivity (0.764), emotional branding (0.752), scent marketing (0.480), store atmosphere (0.345) and visual appeal (0.627) has a positive correlation with customers' impulsive buying behaviour.

4.1 Discussion of Findings

Table 4 showed that audio sensitivity had significant positive effect on customers impulsive buying behaviour ($\beta = 0.318$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Table 7 showed that audio sensitivity had a strong positive correlation with customers' impulsive buying behaviour (0.764). Test of hypotheses one showed that audio sensitivity had significant positive effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria ($0.000 < 0.05$). Audio branding uses appropriate sounds, melodies, and tones to elicit a favourable emotional reaction in consumers. This can result in heightened brand loyalty and a higher probability of making a purchase (Cherubino et al., 2019). This indicates that audio branding is essential in generating immersive experiences in both brick-and-mortar retail locations and digital platforms. Music played within a physical business, along with specific sounds or aural cues related to products, can improve the overall atmosphere, create a favourable shopping experience, and have an impact on customers' buying choices.

Table 4 showed that emotional branding had significant positive effect on impulsive buying behaviour ($\beta = 0.393$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Table 7 showed that emotional branding had a strong positive correlation with customers' impulsive buying behaviour (0.752). Test of hypotheses two showed that emotional branding had significant positive effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria ($0.000 < 0.05$). Emotional branding acknowledges that consumers' purchasing decisions are influenced by their emotions rather than just by rational factors (Srimulyo & Mardiyah, 2020). This indicates that the use of emotional branding assists in establishing a preference for and loyalty towards a brand. Customers that experience an emotional connection with a brand tend to build feelings of affinity, trust, and familiarity.

Table 4 showed that scent marketing had significant positive effect on customers impulsive buying behaviour ($\beta = 0.068$, $p = 0.009 < 0.05$). Table 7 showed that scent marketing had a positive correlation with customers' impulsive buying behaviour (0.480). Test of hypotheses three showed that scent marketing had significant positive effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria ($0.009 < 0.05$). Companies can establish scent-induced recognition and cultivate a robust memory association in consumers' brains by linking a distinct fragrance to their brand (Biswas & Szocs, 2019). This implies that pleasant fragrances might provide a favourable and welcoming ambiance, augmenting shoppers' disposition and entire retail experience. This can result in extended customer durations, heightened contentment, and a higher probability of recurring visits or sales.

Table 4 showed that store atmosphere had significant positive effect on customers impulsive buying behaviour ($\beta = 0.165$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Table 7 showed that store atmosphere had a positive correlation with customers' impulsive buying behaviour (0.345). Test of hypotheses four showed that store atmosphere had significant positive effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria ($0.000 < 0.05$). The store atmosphere is one of the aspects that affect purchasing decisions. Hanafitrah and Widiartanto (2018) demonstrated that the ambiance of a store has a favourable and substantial impact on consumers' purchase choices. This indicates that the ambiance and perception of the ambiance, both outside and inside the store, can create a shopping experience that is memorable for consumers. Furthermore, the store's ambiance can influence consumers' emotions and behaviours, leading to impulsive purchases and a greater inclination to spend more time in the store.

Table 4 showed that visual appeal had significant positive effect on customers impulsive buying behaviour ($\beta = 0.310$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Table 7 showed that visual appeal had a strong positive correlation with customers' impulsive buying behaviour (0.627). Test of hypotheses five showed that visual appeal had significant positive effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria ($0.000 < 0.05$). Strategically crafted graphics, such as a sophisticated logo, attractive packaging, and top-notch images, have the ability to establish a favourable perception and indicate that the company provides superior products or services (Khare & Singh, 2020). This indicates that visual

branding has a vital role in influencing customers purchasing behaviour. The visual aspects of branding have the ability to shape consumers' perception of a brand's level of excellence.

5. Conclusion

The study concluded that neuromarketing practices had significant positive effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour of products sold in shopping malls in South-South Nigeria. Audio branding, emotional branding, scent marketing, store atmosphere and visual branding had significant positive effect on customers' impulsive buying behaviour. The sound elements, including music and soundscapes, employed within a shopping mall have the capacity to establish the overall ambiance and mood of the shopping encounter. Customers that possess a profound emotional attachment to a brand are inclined to exhibit greater loyalty towards said brand. The strategic selection of fragrances can enhance the overall comfort and enjoyment of shopping malls, hence resulting in extended periods of stay and heightened potential for impulsive purchasing. The use of store atmosphere can effectively accentuate promotional activities, discounts, and time-limited offerings. A retail layout that is well-organized has the ability to effectively navigate customers through their shopping experience, thereby increasing their exposure to a wider range of products and stimulating impulsive purchases. The implementation of a cohesive visual branding strategy plays a pivotal role in facilitating brand recognition and recall among customers.

6. Recommendations

- i. Shopping malls should carefully choose background music and audio elements that are in line with their brand's identity and effectively establish a distinct environment.
- ii. Shopping malls could consider implementing narrative and marketing strategies that effectively elicit emotional responses and strongly resonate with their intended demographic.
- iii. It is imperative for shopping malls to exercise caution in the process of scent selection, ensuring that the chosen scents align with the mall's distinct identity and effectively elicit a favourable emotional reaction.
- iv. Shopping malls should prioritise enhancing the physical environment within their premises in order to influence sales.
- v. Shopping malls should be encouraged to use a visually captivating design that incorporates uniform signage, branding features, and aesthetics over the entirety of the mall.

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